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STUDY OF THE LEVEL OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH DOWN SYNDROME

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Keywords: Down syndrome, speech development, diagnostics and correction, preschool age, modification

Abstract. It is known that speech problems are one of the main difficulties for children with Down syndrome. A number of studies from various fields have been devoted to the investigation of this problem. Most researchers, presenting well-founded works on this issue, point out that the low quality of speech in children with Down syndrome creates obstacles to their socialization. The study of psychomotor development in children with Down syndrome shows that if corrective education begins in early childhood, it is possible to prevent speech disorders and delays. On the other hand, many children with Down syndrome are characterized by various hearing problems related to the analysis of auditory information, as well as a small volume of auditory-verbal memory. The aforementioned theoretical and practical studies reveal that the existing impairments significantly reduce the ability of children with Down syndrome to acquire initial speech skills.

Introduction

The analysis of studied materials and reviewed literature revealed the existence of unresolved areas in the diagnosis and correction of speech development in children with Down syndrome, as well as the importance of systematizing and applying both

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diagnostic and corrective methods. The research work undertaken is aimed at developing modified correction programs in accordance with the diagnostic system, alongside the development of constructive directions and methodologies during diagnosis. To achieve our goals, the study involved diagnosing speech development in preschool children (age intervals: 3–4, 4–5, 5–6 years) with Down syndrome and in typically developing children of the same age category, conducted in two phases: initial and dynamic. Based on the initial diagnostic data, it was found that in the speech of typically developing preschool children in the control group, only minor age-appropriate errors were detected. These slight speech errors would disappear as the children develop. However, the results of the first speech examination in each of the preschool-aged children with Down syndrome in the experimental group differed sharply from those in the control group. In both groups – the control and the experimental – the directions of the initial diagnostics were systematized by us and divided into relevant diagnostic criteria for each age group. Although these criteria were based on a hierarchical system, some were subdivided into subcriteria, taking into account the age categories. The presented diagnostic criteria are one of the innovations of this research work.

Main part. As a result of the initial diagnostics of speech development in preschool children with Down syndrome, the following findings were obtained:

In the 3–4 age group of the experiment conducted within the research, two subcriteria from the total of five main diagnostic criteria for speech development were used. In the 3–4 age interval, children with Down syndrome exhibit impairments in the phonetic aspect of speech. Their speech, consisting of sounds and syllable flow, is diffuse, fragmented, and unclear. Disorders in the prosodic aspect of speech are clearly manifested. Often, pitch, timbre, and tempo are impaired. The voice is low, hoarse, nasal, lacking modulation, and monotonous. Speech is often observed only as sound imitation and, in some cases, consists solely of syllable flow. Almost all examined children with Down syndrome displayed phonetic-phonemic disorders such as sound

distortion, omission, substitution, and mixed syllable flow. A characteristic feature of young preschool children with Down syndrome is their developmental delay compared to the average norm. Babbling and smiling in infants with Down syndrome typically begin between eight months and one year of age. Up to the age of three, gestures and sound imitation predominate. Children with Down syndrome often have hearing problems, which result in delays in speech development. In addition to physical hearing impairment, even children with normal hearing exhibit varying degrees of auditory perception disorders (at the level of sounds, syllables, and words) [Abasova, 2018].

In children with Down syndrome, several pathological features can be observed in the anatomical structure of the articulatory apparatus: dentition, tongue, lips, palate, and bite abnormalities. Along with these anatomical pathologies, dystonia of muscle tone is also noted. This dystonia is mainly seen as a paretic state of the muscles. Weak muscle tone and the specific features of the speech apparatus create additional difficulties in forming clear articulation. Due to poor development of expressive speech, communication is limited; however, communicative intent is expressed through gestures, facial expressions, sound imitation, and other attention-getting means. These observations are based on notes taken during various conditions and situations over the research period. Speech delay secondarily affects other developmental spheres, particularly social and cognitive domains

Thus, with these findings in children with Down syndrome, it can be stated with confidence that even partial use of nonverbal communication and sound imitation or syllable flow as a temporary substitute for oral speech helps prevent secondary developmental disorders. At the same time, despite the weakness of expressive speech, the relatively higher development level of receptive speech broadens their possibilities [Abasova, 2017].

In the 4–5 age group of the experiment, five main diagnostic criteria and three subcriteria were used for speech development assessment. Summarizing the diagnostic results of 4–5-year-old children with Down syndrome in the experimental group, it can

be stated that their speech development is characterized by various degrees of delay and, consequently, by different forms of speech disorders. Although passive speech is present, we observed and analyzed the manifestation of active speech with profound impairment symptoms. At this age, initial syllables and monosyllabic words accompanied by gestures began to form. Since speech is extremely weak, it does not fulfill the communicative function.

A characteristic feature of middle preschool-aged children with Down syndrome is developmental delay compared to the average norm. The preschool period is the time when perceptual activity develops in children with intellectual disabilities. This is mainly based on the child's emerging interest in objects, toys, and their attributes. The fifth year of life is a transitional period in the development of perception in a child with intellectual disability. At this stage, children are able to make selections based on examples (color, shape, size). However, their perceptual development is uneven and unstable. It is extremely difficult for them to transfer learned skills from one situation to another [Makarova & Stavseva & Yedakova, 2008].

In the 5–6 age group of the experiment, five main diagnostic criteria and four subcriteria were used for speech development assessment. Determining communicative and play skills clarifies their ability to establish proper cooperation in joint activities. Diagnostics of intellectual development level and general psychomotor condition were also included for each subgroup. Alongside intellectual disability, children with Down syndrome frequently have hearing problems, which lead to speech development delays and result in complex impairments.

The causes of problems arising during speech development include:

- structural features of the articulatory apparatus;
- hypotonia as a form of muscle dystonia;
- auditory perception disorders alongside physical hearing impairments;
- short duration and small capacity of auditory memory;
- organic, local, and functional disorders of the central nervous system;

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- lack of development of higher mental functions such as memory, attention, thinking, and imagination;
- pedagogical neglect. [Strebeleva, 2005]

A characteristic feature of older preschool children with Down syndrome is their developmental delay compared to the average norm. For children with Down syndrome, the preschool period marks the beginning of perceptual development. The child's awakened interest in objects and toys is based on the desire to become familiar with their characteristics and to explore them. The fifth year of life is a turning point in the development of perception in a child with intellectual disability due to Down syndrome. The results of speech development in children aged 5–6 years presented in the study confirm this and indicate that the correction prognosis of pathological speech development criteria provides the basis for development dynamics. At this age, children are already able to make selections based on visual features (color, shape, size). However, their perceptual development is uneven, unstable, and uncertain. During lessons, children who can successfully differentiate properties are unable to distinguish them in daily life or independent activity — for example, when they need to find a certain object in a room. Even when tasks are offered in the form of a game, they show indifference to the outcome. Children who attempt to complete the task usually head towards the goal without considering the necessary conditions to achieve it.

Based on the results of the initial diagnostics, specially modified correction programs were developed for each age group and put into practice. After one year of applying the modified correction programs to the studied children with Down syndrome, the next examination of speech development was conducted during the dynamic phase of speech diagnostics, assessing the children who had undergone the correction process. The system of dynamic assessment was analyzed using the same criteria as in the initial diagnostics.

Taking into account the indicators of the initial diagnostics, during training

it is important to use methods that rely on the child's strengths, especially methods that allow the child to visually perceive adults' speech during the process of mastering speech. Methods in this direction were chosen as a priority in the design of corrective programs. Unlike classical methods of working with children with Down syndrome, the new diagnostic approaches and criteria used in this study led to the creation of a new modified program aimed at forming and developing the speech of these children. Based on the initial diagnostic results, a modified correction program was prepared to implement the correction directions and work plans, considering all the criteria. When selecting the directions and methodologies of the modified program, all diagnostic parameters were taken into account, along with the specific characteristics of each preschool age stage.

In the dissertation research, the modified program consisted of two subprograms. These subprograms were developed taking into account the above-mentioned age categories (3–4 years and 4–6 years). The subprograms combine two main directions:

- The first direction is aimed at developing the receptive (impressive) aspect of speech.
- The second direction is aimed at developing the expressive aspect of speech. Work carried out in these two directions is based on relevant methodologies, and the sessions must necessarily be conducted with a phased structure, following a unified and consistent system.

For both directions of the modified program, the work was based on several stages:

- Work on lexical structure (maintaining structural sequence) in accordance with the goal of each direction, taking into account age categories;
- Work on forming communication tools appropriate for the children under study;
- Work on developing the communicative function using both verbal and nonverbal means;

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- Kinetic and kinesthetic development of the articulatory apparatus and facial muscles, as well as work on facial muscle tone;
- Work on developing the breathing process during speech, including inhalation and exhalation acts;
- Work on forming correct sound pronunciation.

After the modified program was applied to the children under study for one year, it was analyzed through dynamic diagnostics. According to the results of the dynamic diagnostics, the modified program demonstrated positive dynamics in speech development in children with Down syndrome across all age categories studied.

The general conclusions obtained from the analysis of the research are as follows:

1. Taking into account the characteristics of speech development in preschool children with Down syndrome, diagnostics were conducted in two main directions: assessment of the level of development of receptive speech and assessment of the level of development of expressive speech.

2. The speech of preschool children with Down syndrome was diagnosed separately for each age category (3–4; 4–5; 5–6), including the criteria and subcriteria appropriate for each category.

3. For each diagnostic criterion and subcriterion, a corresponding methodological section was developed.

4. The results of the methodologies applied during the diagnostic process were analyzed and reflected in the individual speech map for each child, in accordance with their age category.

5. Based on the results of the diagnostic criteria and subcriteria, a modified correction program was developed for preschool children with Down syndrome, consisting of two subprograms (3–4 years, 4–6 years) with consideration of age categories.

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6. Appropriate correction methodologies were selected for each diagnostic criterion.

7. After the modified correction program was implemented with the studied children with Down syndrome for one year, a second diagnostic assessment – dynamic diagnostics of speech development – was carried out. The dynamic diagnostics revealed progress in speech development.

The results for each item mentioned have been reflected in the corresponding histograms and supplementary materials attached to the dissertation.

The items listed below refer to the novelties of the research work:

1. A unified, systematic diagnostic speech map was developed by selecting initial diagnostic directions, age-appropriate criteria and sub-criteria for each developmental stage, and corresponding diagnostic methods for each criterion.

2. Based on the developed diagnostic speech map, a modified speech development correction program was prepared, consisting of two sub-programs, with methods selected for each age group in accordance with the appropriate structured sequence and systematic progression.

In the course of the research, when working on the speech development of children with Down syndrome, the following factors were taken into account:

- The features, vocabulary, and grammar of our native language;
- The strengths of children with Down syndrome: visual perception, attention, and memory;
- A simplified explanation of the materials so that parents can organize sessions themselves in the absence of a specialist;
- Maintaining a unified approach as the main guiding line in speech development work, to be considered in the sessions of various specialists.

Conclusion

Thus, the examination of the receptive (impressive) and expressive speech of preschool children with Down syndrome makes it possible to distinguish between strong and weak areas of development, which in turn allows for organizing the speech development work system in the correct direction. After obtaining the experimental results, it is essential to take into account the following recommendations in the process of diagnosing and correcting speech development in children with Down syndrome:

1. Social and emotional development is a relatively well-preserved area in individuals with Down syndrome;
2. The ability to retain speech information through the visual analyzer is superior to that of the auditory analyzer;
3. The small capacity of auditory memory requires multiple repetitions to memorize words;
4. Speech impairment may be more severe as a result of hearing impairment;
5. Low muscle tone and the specific structure of the speech apparatus create difficulties in accurate sound articulation;
6. When other forms of communication (gesture, reading) are absent, speech delay can secondarily have a negative impact on other areas of development, especially social and cognitive spheres;
7. Although receptive speech develops to some extent, there are significant delays in the development of expressive speech in children with Down syndrome;
8. Before speaking, children with Down syndrome actively begin to use gestures;
9. Gestures give children the opportunity to communicate, freeing them from many psychological problems;

10. The use of gestures helps parents and close relatives of children with Down syndrome to understand them, while enabling the children to comprehend the speech of others and rapidly expand their vocabulary;

The ability to use various means of communication helps to prevent secondary developmental impairments. As the vocabulary increases, the use of gestures gradually decreases. More precisely, the use of gestures alongside sounds, words, and expressions, within the child's capabilities, is considered valuable.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that a systematically developed, age-specific modified speech development program — targeting both receptive and expressive aspects of speech — leads to measurable improvement in preschool children with Down syndrome. By integrating diagnostic criteria, tailored correction methods, and a unified speech map, the program addressed lexical, communicative, articulatory, and breathing components of speech. The one-year implementation resulted in positive dynamics across all targeted age groups. The findings confirm that accounting for linguistic, cognitive, and motor characteristics, alongside the strategic use of visual supports and gestures, can significantly enhance speech development while preventing secondary developmental delays.

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